

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Machine learning models to forecast dairy cows' productivity in future lactations using Automatic Milking System data

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Proceedings of the European Conference on Precision Livestock Farming, 2026.

This document provides supplementary material supporting the conference paper “Machine learning models to forecast dairy cows' productivity in future lactations using Automatic Milking System data”. It includes additional dataset and methodological details, as well statistical tests results, complementing the main manuscript.

1. Dataset

Data were collected from 16 free-flow Holstein Friesian cow farms located in the Piedmont Region, Italy, all equipped with Astronaut milking robots (Lely©, The Netherlands). The dataset covers the period from 2017 to 2023 and was extracted directly from the Lely© company database. Table 1 presents the total number of cows per lactation in the cleaned dataset.

Table 1: Number of cows per lactation period.

	Lactation period										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Number of cows	4990	3058	1957	1125	557	230	96	38	20	5	1

Data were aggregated at the daily level. To avoid potential bias from incomplete day records, the first and last day of each lactation for each cow were removed. Missing values for Protein% (22.58% observations), Fat% (22.58% observations), and Lactose% (32.93% observations) were replaced by the median of the corresponding lactation period. Missing values for Dry Days (15.55% observations), Milking Robot Rate (1.30% observations), Milking Rate (4.40% observations), and Rumination Time/day (24.17% observations), were replaced by the mode of the corresponding lactation period, using the `modeest::mlv()` method in R (Poncet, 2025). Outliers for Dry Days (19.73% observations) and Delivery Age (13.73% observations) were also replaced by the mode of the corresponding lactation period. The outlier thresholds for Dry Days were set at < 20 days or > 115 days. For Delivery age, they were set for each lactation: for the first lactation, < 550 days or > 1095 days; for subsequent lactations, the range was shifted upward by 365 days per lactation. Outliers of other features were removed using the following thresholds: Days in Milk (DIM) < 50 days or > 500 days (10.86% observations); Milk kg per Day (MPD) > 60 kg/day (5.1% observations); Milking Rate > 8 kg/min (0.05% observations); Refusals/day > 10 (0.43%

observations); Failures/day > 2.5 (0.11% observations). The outlier thresholds were set in consultation with farm and AMS specialists to ensure they reflected realistic biological and operational limits. Table 2 presents the data dictionary and summary statistics of the dataset features after data editing.

Table 2: Definition and descriptive statistics of dataset features utilised in the analysis.

Feature	Definition	Min.	Median	Mean	Max.	Mode
milk_kg_day	Average production (kg) of milk by day.	17.62	35.19	35.70	59.94	31.3
milkings_day	Average number of milking events by day.	1.07	2.75	2.80	5.17	2
milk_kg_min_robot	Average milk production by robot time usage (kg/minutes in the robot).	1.35	5.36	5.50	12.92	4.97
milk_kg_min	Average milk production flow (kg/minutes).	0.60	2.97	3.08	7.89	1.8
refusals_by_day	Average number of refusals events by day.	0.00	0.78	1.22	9.98	0.5
failures_by_day	Average number of failures events by day.	0.00	0.03	0.07	2.37	0
rumination_min_day	Average rumination time (minutes) by day.	0.00	524.79	516.18	661.89	520.20
protein_percent	100 x protein (kg)/milk (kg)	2.65	3.38	3.39	4.13	3.38
fat_percent	100 x fat (kg)/milk (kg)	1.65	3.89	3.93	7.72	3.88
lactose_percent	100 x lactose (kg)/milk (kg)	3.75	4.86	4.86	5.19	4.90
dim	Difference in days between the start and the end date of the lactation period.	51	280	257	499	296
dry_days	Days between the last day of the previous lactation period and the start day of the corresponding lactation period.	20	57	55.78	115	57

The age of the cow in days at the delivery of 551 1116 1256 4474 731
 delivery_age_days the corresponding lactation period.

The dataset features of each lactation were combined with corresponding PG of the merged solution for one or two lactations ahead, depending on the model to be fitted. As shown in section 2.6.2, the number of instances was sufficient to apply supervised ML models only up to the fifth lactation. Thus, four models were fitted to predict PGs one lactation ahead and three models were fitted to predict the PGs two lactations ahead. The one-lactation-ahead models were (i) from the first to the second lactation (model 1→2), (ii) from the second to the third lactation (2→3), (iii) from the third to the fourth lactation (3→4), and (iv) from the fourth to the fifth lactation (4→5). The two-lactation-ahead models were (i) from the first to the third lactation (1→3), (ii) from the second to the fourth lactation (2→4), and (iii) from the third to the fifth lactation (3→5). The nested CV scheme used was the same as that described in Section 6.1, i.e. a 10-fold outer CV and a 5-fold inner CV. Table 3 presents the dataset balance and the number of available data points for each model.

Table 3: Dataset balance and the number of available data points for one- and two-lactation-ahead models.

Lactation features	1	2	3	4	1	2	3
Lactation prediction	2	3	4	5	3	4	5
Number of instances	2321	1157	742	374	1272	579	310
Dataset balance	0.47	0.31	0.32	0.29	0.31	0.33	0.28

2. Computational settings

Decision Tree (DT) models were run using the `DecisionTreeClassifier` of the `scikit-learn` Python library (Pedregosa et al., 2011), with `entropy` as leaves partitioning criterion.

Due to the moderate imbalance in the dataset, the option `class_weight='balanced'` was used. The `max_depth` and `max_features` hyperparameters were optimised with the values presented in Table 4.

Single-Objective Genetic Programming (SOGP) and Multi-Objective Genetic Programming (MOGP) models were run with an adapted version of the General-Purpose Optimization Library (`gpo1`) Python library (Bakurov et al, 2021). Table 5 presents the fixed hyperparameters used in GP models. For SOGP, the selection pressure, mutation probability, and crossover probability hyperparameters were optimised; for MOGP, the tournament size 1 and tournament size 2 hyperparameters were optimised with the values presented in Table 4.

SVM models were run using the SVC model of the `scikit-learn` Python library ((Pedregosa et al., 2011). The option `class_weight='balanced'` was used, making the SVC algorithm use the class frequencies to adjust weights inversely proportional to the class frequencies in the input data. The dataset features were standardised separately in each data split (train, validation, test) with the `StandardScaler` method of the `sklearn.preprocessing.scaler` module of the `scikit-learn` Python library. The `kernel`, `coef0`, and `C` hyperparameters were optimised with the values presented in Table 4.

XGBoost models were run using the `XGBClassifier` model of the `xgboost` Python library (Chen and Guestrin, 2016) with `negative log-likelihood` as eval metric. The proportion between the number of instances in minor and major classes in the training data was used in the `scale minor class` hyperparameter. The `n_estimators`, `max_depth`, and `learning_rate` hyperparameters were optimised with the values presented in Table 4.

NN models were run using the `keras.SequentialModel` of the `tensorflow` Python library (Abadi, et al., 2015). The first hidden layer used 16 neurons and `relu` activation; the

second hidden layer used 8 neurons and `relu` activation; the output layer used 1 neuron and `sigmoid` activation. Between the hidden layers, a `keras.Dropout` layer was included. The `binary_crossentropy` was used as the loss function. The `class_weights` option was used with the `class_weights` defined with the `compute_class_weight` method of the `sklearn.utils` module. As for SVM, dataset features were standardised in each data split (train, validation, test) with the `StandardScaler` method of the `sklearn.preprocessing.scaler` module of the `scikit-learn` Python library. The NNs were run for `epochs = 100` with `batch_size = 32`. The hyperparameters `optimizer`, `learning_rate`, and `dropout_rate` were optimised with the values presented in Table 4. All combinations of the hyperparameter values were tested.

Table 4: Value ranges used to hyperparameter tuning for all models.

Model	Hyperparameter	Values range
DT	<code>max_depth</code>	{3, 4, 5, 6, 7}
	<code>max_features</code>	{d, floor(d × 2 ⁻¹), floor(d)}, where d is the number of features in the dataset.
SOGP	<code>selection_pressure</code>	{0.01, 0.05, 0.07, 0.10}
	<code>mutation_probability</code>	{0.5, 0.7}
	<code>crossover_probability</code>	{0.3, 0.5, 0.7}
MOGP	<code>tournament_size_1</code>	{5, 25, 35, 50}
	<code>tournament_size_2</code>	{2, 3, 4}
SVM	<code>kernel</code>	{linear, sigmoid, rbf}
	<code>coef0</code>	{0.0, 0.5, 1.0}
	<code>C</code>	{0.1, 0.5, 1.0}
XGBoost	<code>n_estimators</code>	{10, 100}
	<code>learning_rate</code>	{0.01, 0.05, 0.10}

NN	max_depth	{3, 5}
	reg_lambda	{0.0, 0.5, 1.0}
	optimizer	{sgd, rmsprop, adam}
	learning_rate	{0.001, 0.01, 0.1}
	dropout_rate	{0.0, 0.05, 0.10, 0.20}

Table 5: Fixed hyperparameters used in Single-objective Genetic Programming (SOGP) and Multi-Objective Genetic Programming (MOGP).

	SOGP	MOGP
Generations - tuning phase	150	150
Generations - fitting phase	500	500
Population size	500	500
Elitism	True	True
Reproduction	False	False
Mutation operator	subtree mutation	subtree mutation
Mutation probability	optimised	0.9
Crossover operator	swap crossover	swap crossover
Crossover probability	optimised	0.1
Function set	{+, -, ×, ÷}	{+, -, ×, ÷}
Fitness function	f1-score	obj 1: f1-score obj 2: structural complexity

3. P-values

Table 6: P-values adjusted with Bonferroni correction of the Dunn test for comparing the F1-score of the different models on predicting the cows' Productivity Groups for one lactation ahead. Bold values highlight the significant differences with level of significance $\alpha < 0.01$.

First to Second	DT	MOGP	NN	SOGP	SVM
MOGP	1.0000				

NN	1.0000	1.0000			
SOGP	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000		
SVM	1.0000	0.4169	1.0000	1.0000	
XGBoost	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000	1.0000

Second to Third

	DT	MOGP	NN	SOGP	SVM
MOGP	1.0000				
NN	0.0209	0.0297			
SOGP	1.0000	1.0000	0.0002		
SVM	0.3178	0.2434	0.0000	1.0000	
XGBoost	1.0000	1.0000	0.0010	1.0000	1.0000

Third to Fourth

	DT	MOGP	NN	SOGP	SVM
MOGP	1.0000				
NN	0.7005	1.0000			
SOGP	1.0000	0.6287	0.2105		
SVM	1.0000	0.2037	0.0558	1.0000	
XGBoost	1.0000	1.0000	0.6638	1.0000	1.0000

Fourth to Fifth

	DT	MOGP	NN	SOGP	SVM
MOGP	1.0000				
NN	0.0012	0.0268			

SOGP	1.0000	1.0000	0.0014		
SVM	1.0000	1.0000	0.0004	1.0000	
XGBoost	1.0000	1.0000	0.0006	1.0000	1.0000

Table 7: P-values adjusted with Bonferroni correction of the Dunn test for comparing the F1-score of the different models on predicting the cows' Productivity Groups for two lactations ahead. Bold values highlight the significant differences with level of significance $\alpha < 0.01$.

First to Third					
	DT	MOGP	NN	SOGP	SVM
MOGP	0.7103				
NN	0.0007	0.1941			
SOGP	1.0000	0.4484	0.0003		
SVM	1.0000	0.3646	0.0002	1.0000	
XGBoost	1.0000	0.2322	0.0001	1.0000	1.0000
Second to Fourth					
	DT	MOGP	NN	SOGP	SVM
MOGP	1.0000				
NN	0.2176	1.0000			
SOGP	1.0000	0.0713	0.0023		
SVM	1.0000	0.1226	0.0047	1.0000	
XGBoost	1.0000	0.1270	0.0049	1.0000	1.0000
Third to Fifth					
	DT	MOGP	NN	SOGP	SVM
MOGP	1.0000				

NN	0.0671	0.2314			
SOGP	1.0000	1.0000	0.0100		
SVM	1.0000	1.0000	0.0127	1.0000	
XGBoost	1.0000	1.0000	0.0176	1.0000	1.0000

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